

NATURAL BLOOD THINNERS.

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For many years, doctors have used willow bark to improve the quality of blood. This tool does not have a serious negative effect on the mucous membrane of the stomach. To prepare the remedy, the following steps must be taken:

1. 200 ml of boiling water is poured into 1 tablespoon of bark.
2. Boil the mixture for 10 minutes.
3. Rest for more than 30 minutes.
4. Then boiling water is added to the tincture until it reaches the initial amount.
5. Drink 2 tablespoons 3 times a day before meals.

Yellow corn plant has a strong blood thinning effect. However, before using this plant, you should consult a specialist, because there are some contraindications to its use.

In the spring, when the days are warm and the sun is shining, leeching (girudotherapy), wearing a hijama (blood drawing) is one of the factors that stimulate the renewal of blood in the body and the rejuvenation of a person. In general, bleeding and constipation (constipation) are primarily caused by poor diet and inactivity. Due to the negative effects of constipation, hemorrhoids develop. A healthy person should have regular bowel movements every day.

As a result of constipation, the body is poisoned. The patient has a headache. Sometimes he is restless. He does not realize that the cause is constipation and takes medicine for headaches. These artificial drugs harm the heart and kidneys. At that time, the sick person should eat coarse fiber, i.e. black, bran bread, which contains a lot of fiber, red beet salad, steamed sugar beet. Boiled turshak with fennel seeds also makes the stomach move.

Dill seed tincture has been widely used in folk medicine to prevent meteorism. To do this, put a teaspoon of seeds in a half-liter teapot and brew it instead of tea. It should be brewed in the evening and drunk in the morning on an empty stomach. Medicinal fennel seeds also increase breast milk and prevent colic in the baby.

Natural laxatives are used in folk medicine for constipation. Mackai sano plant (sold in pharmacies) drinking yogurt or cottage cheese at room

temperature on an empty stomach also relieves constipation. Drinking still mineral water with meals cleans the stomach.

Meaty, dark and indigestible foods should not be eaten three days before using any laxative. Instead, eat easily digestible, dietary, whole grain products (buckwheat), oats (perlovka), lentils (chechevisa) and salads. Surgi not only cleanses the intestines. It also improves blood composition. Removes spots on the face and rejuvenates the skin.

During the cold season, when the reserves of vitamins and macro and microelements in the body decrease, our ancestors and mothers used to prepare dishes such as halim and sumak from groats and harvested wheat. They cooked dumplings from different grains. Dishes from various spring vegetables were served on the tables. These dishes are also useful.

The best results are given by infusions containing the following plants:

- Mint;
- Yellow donut;
- Red Sebarga;
- Melissa;
- Labaznik;
- Valeriana;
- Namatak;
- Hawthorn

These plants can be used at home in the form of tea, tinctures and tinctures.

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